

ANALYSIS OF MECHANICAL PROPERTY IN VARTM-MANUFACTURED CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

In the field of carbon fiber composite materials (CFRP), research on next-generation manufacturing technologies such as high-cycled RTM (resin-transfer molding) and VaRTM (vacuum-assisted RTM) has been actively conducted. Large molds are currently possible. These methods require that the fiber substrate is formed prior to molding; this preforming process takes a significant amount of time. Moreover, the accuracy and quality of the preforming process affects the molding's mechanical properties. Recently, discussions have focused on automating this process, but it is done manually.

In this study, three CFRP preforms were manufactured. (Figure 1)

This test method evaluated "Fibre-reinforced plastic composites -- Determination of apparent interlaminar shear strength by short-beam method" according to Japanese Industrial Standards (JIS K 7057). JIS K 7057 is the popular examination standard in the field of fibre-reinforced plastic composites. This method is used to aim at quality control and quality comparison of different materials. Specimens were cut from a strip of the flat parts of the manufactured preform. All specimens were 20.0 mm long, 18.0 mm wide and 2.2 mm thick. In the bending method, the radius of the support was 2.0 mm; the radius of the penetrator was 2.5 mm; and the span between the points of force was 11.0 mm.

As for the results, interlaminar shear strength clearly differed in the three specimens even though they were manufactured using the same process. We thought these differences were caused by lack of accuracy, because fiber directions were not settled.

In the future, new preforms will be manufactured by changing fiber orientation. Thus we will research the differences in interlaminar shear strength based on the fiber orientation's variation and resin impregnation. We will not cut the flat parts, but will focus on other parts of the manufactured preforms to assay the mechanical property influence, such as the interlaminar shear strength, the tensile properties and resin rich area.

1 INTRODUCTION

Within the carbon fiber reinforced plastic industry (CFRP), the VaRTM molding method (Vacuum assisted Resin Transfer Molding) and the high-cycle RTM method (Resin Transfer Molding) are used for large molds. Research for the next generation of molding manufacturing technology is being actively pursued and used widely. With the VaRTM method, because there is no need to install equipment which will apply high temperatures and pressure, and because it can be used for complex shapes, it is considered a cost efficient and high-quality molding method. However, it requires that a fiber base-material preform is manufactured before molding. Manufacturing the preform takes a lot of time, and the accuracy of the preform affects the mechanical properties of the mold. In recent years, research into the automatic manufacturing of this preform have continued to progress; however, the majority are manufactured by hand. Research of CFRP molding focusing on the flow and hardening of resins is currently underway, but the effect of the worker's manual labor is also considered to be an important factor. For example, in conjunction with analyzing the movements and work process of workers in hand lay-up molding and spray-up molding [1, 2, 3], Kikuchi et al. have begun tests that aim to scientifically explain the manual labor of workers in molding, such as investigating the subtly different effects that each worker had on their molding [4].

This research focused on VaRTM molding. However, this form of molding also has manual labor involved in its process, which is considered to have a large effect on the finished molding. Thus, we investigated the difference in the time it took the subjects, all of whom have varying years of experiences working with composite materials, to manufacture the preform, as well as their working postures, the way they use the manufacturing tools during the manufacturing process. Also, we examined the mechanical properties of the test panel produced by VaRTM molding, and how these factors affect the accuracy of the mold.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

2.1 Experimental Materials

We used a fiber base-material produced by SAERTEX, a carbon fiber NCF (Non-Crimp Fabric). The fixing agent was powder. (see Table 1) And we used a matrix epoxy resin produced by Axon Inc., EPOLAM5015 (main agent) and EPLOAM5015 (curing agent).

2.2 Molding Method

In order to stack the layers in the shape shown in Fig.1 we manufactured the preform by layering the carbon fiber NCF, setting the silicon mold to produce a hat-shaped mold in the center, and then layering the same fiber, based on the layer structure chart shown in Table 1. The preform manufacturing process is comprised of three sections. Section I and III are the stacking sequence of the skin section and the stacking sequence of the hat-shaped mold, and section II is setting the mold in order to create the hat shape (Table 2 shows the preform manufacturing process). After manufacturing the preform, resin is infused into the preform using the VaRTM method. After infusion, the preform is hardened at 25°C for 12 hours, 40°C for 2 hours, and then 80°C for another 2 hours.

We informed the three subjects of the work process order and how to conduct the work beforehand, and provided them all with exactly the same tools. We also made them use a fiber base-material that had been cut the same size as the mold as well as auxiliary materials for the molding, all of which had been cut the same sizes. However, despite specifying the tape used as an auxiliary material, we left the length to cut it and where to stick it up to the judgment of the subjects. The years of experience of the three subjects (how many years they have been working with composite materials) in order of most years of experience to least is Expert, Elementary and Beginner, with 8 years, 1.5 years, and 0 years of experience (first time) respectively.

Table 1: Stacking Sequence

Skin Section			Hat-shaped Section		
ply #	Fiber Orientation (Angular Degree)	Thickness (mm)	ply #	Fiber Orientation (Angular Degree)	Thickness (mm)
1	[+/- 45]	0.25	1	[+/- 45]	0.25
2	[0 / 90]	0.25	2	[0 / 90]	0.25
3	[90 / 0]	0.25	3	[90 / 0]	0.25
4	[-/+ 45]	0.25	4	[-/+ 45]	0.25
Total		1.00	Total		1.00

Figure 1: CFRP perform

Table 2: Process Flow of Manufacturing Preform

I	the Skin Section (n=1~4)
	n ply Fiber orientation confirmation
	n ply Stacking sequence
II	Installation Section
	setting the Silicon mold Fillers installation
III	the Hat-Shaped Mold Section (n=1~4)
	n ply Fiber orientation confirmation
	n ply Stacking sequence

2.3 Evaluation Method

In order to analyze the movement of the subjects, we watched video footage, interviewed.

【Video footage】

For the subject's working posture and how they used the tools (iron), we divided up the time they spent on each of the processes and compared their actions based on the footage that captured each of the subjects creating the preform. A third party observer who has no connection with the subjects was in charge of checking the video footage in order to objectively evaluate their performance. (shown in Fig. 6)

【Interview with the Subjects】

After examining the video footage, in order to compare the relationships between the subjective data (information obtained during the interview) and the objective data (actual performance), the same subjects manufactured the same molding.

【Interlaminar Shear Strength Test】

We cut out specimens from the skin section of the molds after the VaRTM, shown in Fig. 2, measured the interlaminar shear strength, and compared the results. The molds were evaluated using the short beam method, based on the JIS standard (K7057).

Figure 2: Specimen Cutoff (Interlaminar Shear Strength Test)

【Tensile Test】

We cut out the experimental specimens as displayed in Fig.3 from the skin section of the molds produced by VaRTM molding, and then tensile strength of each specimen was measured for comparison. Tensile test was carried out in accordance with the JIS standard (K7164). However, it has to be noted that because specimens were not of sufficient length, each specimen was cut out with 10:1 ratio, the same ratio as specified by JIS standard.

【Measurement of Elasticity】

Elasticity was calculated from the results of the tensile test.

【Observation of Cutting Section】

As Fig.3 shows, six parts were cut out for the purpose of observation from each mold. The midsection and the two ends of both the upper and lower part of the silicon (40mm in diameter for each) were cut out for observation.

- Experiment device : KEYENCE Digital Microscope VHX-900
- Condition : 20-fold magnification

Figure 3: Specimens Cutoff (Tensile Test and Observation of Cutting Section)

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Fig.4 shows the time required for each respective worker-the expert, the elementary-level, and the beginner worker-to complete the molding process.

The underside of the skin surface after the VaRTM showed the largest difference in the workers' level of experience (shown in Fig. 5). The experimental procedures for this research consisted of the subjects placing the silicon mold in order to create the hat shape, and then proceeding with the layering. However, if the worker does not make the fiber base-material fit and stack the layers while pressing an iron against the edges of the silicon mold, the edge line will rise up after the VaRTM, as is shown in Fig. 5, causing a difference in product accuracy. The preform's level of accuracy affects the mechanical properties of the mold. However, even in this experiment, the preform made by the subjects with little experience had visible edge lines in their specimens on the underside of the skin layer. Thus, this time, we analyzed the working posture and approach to applying the iron, which was used to join the fiber base-material.

Figure 4: Time Required for Each Worker and Process

Figure 5: The underside of the skin surface

①Grip Used on the Iron

Expert: Held the iron in his hand with four fingers, gripping it tightly.

Elementary and Beginner: Held the iron in their hands with three fingers, using their index fingers for support.

【Result of the Interview】

Expert & Elementary : Accordingly changed their grip depending on where the iron needs to be pressed on. However, it was not that they applied pressure to the molds, rather they were more conscious about adhesion between fiber and the iron. They were paying attention to the straightness of the angle of fiber orientation.

Beginner : Was conscious about the grip so that he could apply strength and press fiber with the whole heating unit of the iron.

②Posture Used to Apply the Iron

Expert: Changed the angle of his body based on where he was pressing the iron and put all of his strength into pressing the iron against the preform because his body was positioned in a way that it looked as though he might topple forwards. (see Fig. 6)

Elementary and Beginner: Stood straight and rarely moved. They attempted to join the fiber base-material using their hands and the heat from the iron.

【Result of the Interview】

Expert : Merely tried to apply strength evenly during the working process. He did not pay much attention to the working posture.

Elementary : Did not pay much attention to the working posture. But, he bent down to check the test piece when fiber adhesion was not appropriate.

Beginner : Paid attention to his hand strength. He tried to apply pressure by his hands thinking that heat of the iron is greatly related to layering.

③Holding the fiber base with the opposite hand to the one holding the iron

Expert & Elementary : As Fig. 6 shows, their hand holding the fiber base followed the other hand with the same speed when moving the iron (both hands were close to each other all the time).

Beginner : His hand holding the fiber base did not move with the iron (holding hand always stayed on the edge of the fiber base).

【Result of the Interview】

Expert : Made sure that the fiber would not move, and he tried to partially hold the fiber base so that the iron could run parallel to the fiber direction.

Elementary : Was not conscious about the hand holding the fiber base because he merely performed in the easier way for him to work.

Beginner : Fixed the position of his hand holding the fiber base because he tried to prevent adhesion between fiber and the iron from causing separation of the layers while he was pressing the iron.

④Method Used to Apply the Iron

We informed the subjects of the work procedures beforehand. However, aside from using the iron, we left how the fiber base-material is fitted into the mold up to each of the subjects. The reason for this is because that the purpose of this research was to increase preform accuracy through the worker by establishing the Beginner's way of learning, so we did not delve into explaining the finer points of molding.

Various differences arose in the order, places and angles in which each of the subjects applied the iron.

Thus, we divided the places on the molding that the iron was pressed against into five different places (see Fig. 7) We compared how long each of the subjects pressed the iron against the molding in the first ply layers and fourth ply layers for the hat-shaped mold (see Fig. 8).

Expert: Spent time on the edges and applied the iron while paying attention to the angle it was on because he understood the importance of fitting the fiber base-material into the edges of the silicon mold.

Elementary and Beginner: Spent a lot of time applying the iron to the skin surface rather than fitting it into the mold, attempting to secure the fiber base-material and quickly continue onto the next step.

【Result of the Interview】

Expert : Pressed the iron against the mold with paying attention to the fillers placed on the edge lines, in order to prevent the fiber from slipping off. He tried to keep the straightness of the angle and protect the fillers and the fiber base. Also, he tried to start applying the iron from the center of the fiber and stretch out twists and wrinkles. He applied the iron from the right side of the mold, because he is right-handed.

Elementary : Did not pay attention to the edge lines, but he tried to apply the iron from the center of the mold so that the mold would not move, as though he was releasing air from fibers. He applied the iron from the right side of the mold, because he is right-handed.

Beginner : Consciously applied the iron against the skin surface because fibers layered within the skin would come out to the surface if the edge of the iron is applied to the mold. He applied the iron from the right side of the mold, because he is right-handed.

Figure 6: Posture of Expert

Throughout the entire process, before applying the iron, the expert fitted the fiber base-material into the mold, pressed down the fiber base-material and mold with the hand that was not holding the iron so they would not move, and adjusted the iron's angle and the strength he was holding it down with, causing the fiber base-material to fill in excellently. For his posture when applying the iron, he stacked the layers while applying the iron, with his entire body pressing against the fiber base-material, preventing looseness between the layers. After the VaRTM, the resin flowed evenly into the fiber base-material, achieving a finish so clean that it is unclear where the mold is positioned just by inspecting it. However, the Elementary and Beginner subjects with little experience did not pay attention to the edges of the silicon mold (Fig. 7) when stacking the layers, but instead focused on

securing the skin surface with the iron so that the fiber base material would not move. Thus, the fiber base-material was not properly stacked onto the edge line, resulting in the mold fitting being loose for the entire layering process, and sharp edge lines forming on the silicon mold on the underside of the skin surface after the VaRTM.

Figure 7: Places the Iron was Pressed

Figure 8: Length of Time and Places Each of the Subjects Pressed the Iron

Figure 9: Differences in the Apparent Interlaminar Shear Strength in Each of the Subjects

Fig 10: Differences in the Tensile Strength in Each of the Subjects

Figure 11: Differences Elasticity in Each of the Subjects

Figure 12: Differences in the Tensile Strength in Each of the Subjects

As a result of observation with the microscope, residual resin was found within the edge lines that were not recognized by naked eye observation. (shown in Fig. 12) Also, many holes were observed in between the layers.

It was clear that because the last step in the process is vacuuming that, while that no major problems occur in the skin surface if the angle and other aspects of the fiber orientation have been properly layered, if you do not apply strength and use the iron evenly on when layering, the mold edge lines show on the underside of the product. Because we were able to check the differences in product quality just by looking at them, this time, we cut specimens out from skin sections which did not have edge lines showing and were also predicted to have few dispersions and twists in the fiber orientation (at the very least, they appeared exactly the same just by looking at them), and measured the interlaminar shear strength. However, as is shown in Fig. 9, differences were observed in the interlaminar shear strength among specimens in order of how many years' experience they had (Expert, Elementary and Beginner).

However, as is shown in Fig. 10 and 11, with regard to tensile strength and elasticity, it was shown that years of experience did not lead to any differences. Rather, these parameters were dependent on fiber strength.

4 DISCUSSION

As a result of the tensile test and the interlaminar shear strength test conducted in order to attain the mechanical property data, it was found that, contrary to expectation, difference in the years of experience led to variance in the shear strength on the skin surface, and that the value of the shear strength was proportional to the years of experience of each performer. However, the tensile test did not show any relevance between the years of experience and the value of the tensile strength. Thus it conducts the interlaminar shear strength test in different points. This study gave much focus on the difference in the level of each performer's skills and observation of their working motions, which was why the body of the samples for the experiment was very limited. In the future studies, it will be necessary to measure the strength of an integral molding by industrial CT scanning and compression test with focusing around the resin line parts where our study discovered some obvious differences depending on the skills. It will be able to elucidate the opaque parts that were hardly verified by the cutting sections observation done by microscope. Through the course of the interviews, it was confirmed that the subjects with less years of experience tended to lack the understanding of the way of adapting the fiber base to the silicon mold which is of great importance for the molding, and also the understanding of the effective way of gripping the iron with consideration to the fiber orientation. As a result of this lack of knowledge, lines appeared on the backside of the molds manufactured by the inexperienced subjects, and observation with the microscope identified some residual resin within the edge lines. It can be predicted that the force and places of pressing the iron exerts the great influence to the completed product. In addition, as many holes were observed between the fibers, it would also be necessary to measure the content of the voids in each mold.

5 CONCLUSION

In the future, in order to improve the accuracy of the mold and to enable the manufacturing of the products with the uniform quality, it will be required to verify the preferable conditions for the manufacturing of the preform with the uniform precision by measuring V_f , void content of the mold, pressure on the fiber base in contact with the heating unit of the iron, and so forth. With regard to the areas and the direction where the iron is pressed, we will conduct several analyses under various molding angle conditions to ascertain the causes of the difference in strength and eventually to minimize the difference of strength resulting from angles and variance of fiber orientation. It will also be necessary to have the subjects more conscious to the relationships between the verbal recognition and their action (behavior patterns resulting from the way of using tools or the way of placing fiber base) by giving an appropriate instruction to the subjects under the uniform working condition. In order to enable any performer to manufacture the preform mold and the products with the uniform accuracy, our future researches shall be aimed at creating the working guidelines that explain an effective behavior patterns as to where a performer should focus on, with recognizing the vital points of the working procedures at the first glance. So we need to measure interlaminar shear strength of each specimens in different points to compare and analyze the mechanical property. Therefore These working guidelines will enable the handlings as well as the automation of the manufacturing process.

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